

Evaluation of the Quality of Online Learning Services (Case Study at UPBJJ-UT Ternate)

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ABSTRACT: *The purpose of this study was to examine and analyze the effect of pre-registration services, availability of basic material books, tutoring services and final exams on the quality of student learning during the COVID-19 pandemic. This research is an empirical research using probability sampling technique. Data was obtained by distributing questionnaires to 351 undergraduate students who registered for the 2020 academic year at UPBJJ-UT Ternate. Data analysis was performed using multiple regression analysis. The results showed that online registration services, online facility services, basic material book services, had no effect on the quality of online learning. While the final exam service affects the Quality of Online Learning.*

KEYWORDS- *Evaluation, Service Quality, Online Learning*

I. INTRODUCTION

Since the COVID-19 pandemic hit the world, it has affected various aspects of life, including the aspect of education which is a basic need of human life. According to Napitulu (2020), the ongoing Covid-19 pandemic has brought changes to distance learning methods. Based on data obtained, as of June 18, 2020, the number of people exposed to Covid-19 in Indonesia reached 42,762 people or an increase of 1,331 people (Covid-19 Handling Task Force, 2020). While in North Maluku itself, the number of people exposed to Covid-19 until August 2020 reached 1,729 (Kieraha.com). This condition causes the government to provide a policy so that all education and learning services are carried out online by paying attention to the health and safety of students, as well as maintaining the quality of education and the achievement of student competencies. This is a challenge for every educational institution. Universitas Terbuka (UT) followed up on this policy by issuing the UT Chancellor's Regulation Number 721 of 2020 concerning Education Service Policies in a COVID-19 Pandemic Situation in article 2 which states that all educational services are carried out online based on predetermined standards. Although previously some students conducted lectures with a face-to-face system, UT in dealing with these conditions did not experience obstacles that burdened the university and the students themselves, because since 2013 UT began implementing SIMINTAS in the field of Distance Learning Management to replace Academic Administration Services. UT also ensures that the academic quality of distance learning has been recognized nationally and internationally (<https://lppm.ut.ac.id/penjaminan-mutu>), so that students who previously attended face-to-face lectures can also adapt.

In North Maluku, 70% of the Open University students at UPBJJ-UT Ternate are scattered in all districts whose territory is an archipelagic country. However, there are still many areas that have not been reached by the internet network. This condition causes when there is a Work From Home (WFH) recommendation by the government during the pandemic, students experience problems in participating in the online lecture process. According to (Tirziu, AM, & Vrabie, 2015) to improve the quality of online learning, at least there is the involvement of teachers, students and technology that can ensure the online learning process can run well, so as to provide student learning satisfaction.

Satisfaction is a person's feelings of pleasure or disappointment that arise after comparing his perceptions/impressions of the performance or results of a product with his expectations. The results of the study (Maulana & Hamidi, 2020) show that online learning has a positive impact on practical courses. Then the results of research (Adijaya & Santosa, 2018) on student perceptions of online learning, show students feel online

learning is less supportive in the teaching and learning process, so lecturers can facilitate it by creating groups on social media to interact and improve the quality of learning.

Several studies have been conducted related to online learning, for example Kusdiyantoro (2019), conducted research on the effectiveness of online learning models in Indonesian language lectures using the Online Interactive Learning Model (OILM) technique. The results showed that this learning model was able to increase the absorption of lecture material by students with an increase of more than 81%. Tantri (2018), conducted research on social presence in online learning based on students' perspectives in open and distance education. The results showed that online learning had a positive effect on aspects of connectedness, learning aspects, and social emotional aspects. Mostofa et al. (2019), conducted research on the formulation of an online lecture model by utilizing the government's official website as an effort to reduce disparities in the quality of higher education. The results show that the online lecture system has a positive contribution to encourage disparities in the quality of higher education in Indonesia. While the research results of Raharjo et al. (2018), showing that the services provided by UT such as public services, registration services, tutorial services, practicum services, teaching materials services and exam administration services have been fulfilled.

This study develops research conducted by Napitupulu (2020) and Raharjo et al. (2018). Napitupulu conducted a study on the Impact of the Covid-19 Pandemic on Distance Learning Satisfaction. While Raharjo et al. assessing student satisfaction with UT's academic services. The results showed that more than 50% of students were satisfied with the services provided by UT, such as: public services, registration services, tutorial services, practicum/practicum services, teaching materials services and administrative services. In this study, the researcher added the online module provision service as an independent variable.

From the specific objectives mentioned above, the urgency of this research is that with the new development concept, the researcher tries to build a proposal regarding the quality of online learning through the synthesis of academic contemplation from supporting theories. In this study, a new concept is proposed, namely the theory: Satisfaction, quality and service theory. This concept is expected to play a role in increasing the satisfaction of Student Academic Services while at the same time increasing the achievement of UT students at UPBJJ-UT Ternate.

II. LITERARY REVIEW

Quality Theory

According to Kusdiyantoro (2019), in improving education services there are several dimensions of service quality in the form of tangible, reliability, responsiveness, assurance and empathy. In this study, quality theory is used to explain the quality of online learning. Quality is the hallmark of a product/service that can provide satisfaction to its users. Tdjiptono (2002), classifies the quality of a service which consists of three main components, namely:

1. Technical Quality, namely components related to service outputs received by customers, for example;
 - Search Quality, which is the quality that customers can evaluate before buying, for example price.
 - Experience Quality, namely quality that can only be assessed by customers after buying or consuming services, for example timeliness, service and neatness of service results.
 - Credence Quality, which is a quality that is difficult for customers to measure even though they have consumed a service, for example the quality of surgery
2. Functional Quality, which is a component related to the quality of the way services are delivered.
3. Corporate image is the profile, reputation, general image and special attractiveness of a company.

According to Parasuraman et al., (1988) in Ikhsan (2011), service quality is more difficult to measure than product quality because service characteristics are included in the intangibility, heterogeneity and inseparability of service products. These characteristics make service quality more abstract and difficult to understand than product quality. However, the definition of quality generally includes the following elements: meeting customer expectations, aspects of the product, service, people, process and environment, and ever-evolving criteria which means that a product now includes quality, but at other times it may not. again to be quality. So quality is something dynamic related to products, services, people, processes and the environment.

Registration

Students who have been registered as UT students must register for courses to be able to take part in academic activities such as tutorials, practice/practicum and Final Semester Exams. Students register for courses that will be registered at the UPBJJ-UT Office and students will get a Registration Payment Information Sheet (PRS) which is used to pay tuition at the bank. PRS that has been validated by the bank is used as proof of

registration (ut.ac.id, 2020). Each course is assigned a code indicating the code of study program, level of education, academic year, and sequence of courses. How to register for the course, by observing the following steps:

1. Registration of courses to be registered at UPBJJ-UT, can be done by coming in person, by telephone, letter, fax, email, or sms to UPBJJ-UT.
2. Receive LIP Registration from UPBJJ-UT.
3. Check the correctness of Registration at PRS. If there are still errors, immediately inform the UPBJJ-UT officers to be corrected.
4. Pay tuition fees directly at the Bank or through an ATM in accordance with the amount of the bill listed on the PRS, before the payment deadline stated on the PRS. Thus officially becoming a student and registered as a participant in the Final Semester Examination.

Tutorial

Tutorial is academic assistance or tutoring by tutors to students. The goal is to help smooth the independent learning process of students, both individually and in groups. Tutorials are conducted face-to-face or online based on the concept of self-study. Because the tutorial has the same principle as learning, which is to help students learn, the general procedure for tutorials is the same as the general procedure for learning. Thus, in general tutorial activities consist of initial activities, core activities, and closing activities. To be able to activate students, tutorial activities must be carried out using various methods. Tutors must strive for optimal student activity and participation. Thus, the tutor acts more as a facilitator (Wardani, 2005).

Teaching materials

Teaching materials are an important part in the implementation of Distance Education. Teaching materials have an important role in the implementation of the Distance Education program, because students have relatively less contact with teachers when compared to students who take conventional learning. Teaching materials must be able to stimulate and support the formation of a quality learning experience for independent students. Teaching materials must also be able to turn on imagination and mental activity, trigger learning motivation, and encourage participants to carry out meaningful learning activities (Ubaidah, 2019).

Along with the development of information technology, distance learning teaching materials are now also available online. Teaching materials and information technology are used to convey lesson content, which in conventional learning systems is delivered directly by resource persons. This is in accordance with the meaning of the implementation of distance education programs, namely the form and learning situation where students are separated both by location and time from learning resources (Ubaidah, 2019).

Online Exam System

One type of evaluation of learning outcomes at UT is the Online Semester Final Examination (OSFE). Online exams are intended to provide opportunities for students to: (a) take exams with conflicting exam hours (an exam for one of the conflicting courses can be taken through OSFE), (b) take exams outside the written exam schedule that has been determined in the academic calendar UT. The form of online exam questions is divided into multiple choice tests and essay tests. For multiple choice exams, the answers are done directly on the computer online, while for essay exams, the answers are done in the exam answer book.

Based on the phenomena and research gaps mentioned above, the hypotheses of this research are:

- H1: Online registration service satisfaction affects the achievement of online learning quality
- H2: Satisfaction with online tutorial services affects the quality of online learning
- H3: Satisfaction with online teaching materials affects the quality of online learning
- H4: Online Final Examination Service Satisfaction affects the quality of online learning

III. RESEARCH METHODS

The population in this study were all students of the 20201 Registration Period and were active in online tutorial activities at UPBJJ-UT Ternate. The sampling method was carried out by purposive sampling. The type of data used in this study is quantitative data which is also self-report data, namely research data in the form of opinions, attitudes, experiences or also referred to as primary data, where the data source is directly from the original source or not through an intermediary. Classification of data is classified into verbal and written. Verbal

respondents were given in response to questions posed by researchers, written respondents were given responses to written questions posed by respondents through questionnaires. The analytical tool used in this research is Multiple Linear Regression analysis.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Descriptive statistics

Table 1.
 Descriptive Statistics

Variable	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Online Registration	229	3,17	5,00	4,0653	0,38485
Online Tutorials	229	2,50	5,00	4,0295	0,51667
Online Teaching Materials	229	2,67	5,00	3,9083	0,57455
Online Exam System	229	3,00	5,00	3,9450	0,45493
Quality of Online Learning	229	3,08	5,00	3,9624	0,40715
Valid N (listwise)	229				

Source: primary data processed by SPSS (2021)

Based on Table 1, the number of samples is 229. The standard deviation value of each variable is smaller than the mean value which indicates that the data in this study are spread around the arithmetic mean.

Hypothesis Testing Results

Table 2.
 Partial Hypothesis Testing Results

Information	B	t Table	Sig
Constants	0,969	3,073	0,002
Online Registration Service	0,023	0,129	0,898
Online Tutorial Service	-0,071	-0,477	0,634
Online Teaching Material Service	-0,158	-1,648	0,101
Online Exam Service	0,443	2,453	0,015*
R= 0,652 RSquare =0,425 AdjusR2= 0,407 F = 0,000 Sig= *0,05			

Source: SPSS Data Processing, 2021

Based on the regression equation Table 2 can be interpreted several things, including:

1. The online registration service variable has a positive direction regression coefficient of 0.023. This illustrates that if there is an increase in online registration services as much as 1 time, then the quality of online learning will increase by 0.023, assuming other independent variables are held constant.
2. The online tutorial service variable has a negative-directed regression coefficient of -0.071. This illustrates that if there is an increase in online tutorial services by 1 time, the quality of online learning will decrease by -0.071 with the assumption that other independent variables remain constant.
3. The online module service variable has a negative trending regression coefficient, which is -0.158. This illustrates that if there is an increase in online teaching material services as much as 1 time, then the quality of online learning will decrease by 0.158 assuming other independent variables remain constant.
4. The service variable for the online final exam has a positive regression coefficient of 0.443. This illustrates that if there is an increase in online final exam services by 1 time, the quality of online learning will increase by 0.443, assuming other independent variables are held constant.

V. Discussion

Online Registration Services Affect Online Learning Quality

The results of hypothesis testing indicate that online registration services have no effect on the quality of online learning. Then the hypothesis (H1) is rejected. This is because in general students have felt fast with online registration services from banks, responsiveness from employees to registration problems faced by students, good socialization related to getting payment information sheets before registration is carried out and ease of service interaction between employees. UT and Students. So that the form of registration services has become a habit which is not an important indicator in influencing student achievement. The results of this study are not in line with the research of Maria et al. (2016) which shows that online services have an effect on students' intentions in completing learning.

Online Tutorial Services Affect the Quality of Online Learning

The results showed that online tutorial services had no effect on the quality of online learning, so hypothesis (H2) was rejected. This result is not in line with Dewi's (2001) research which shows that learning facilities have a direct effect on online learning. This is because in general students are familiar with online website facilities, online bookstores. Ease of accessing teaching materials is a habit that has been entrenched in an open university environment so it is not an indicator that can affect student achievement and the quality of online learning.

However, what is interesting in this study is that the value of the online tutorial service variable is negative, indicating that students actually do not fully expect online tutorial services. As stated in the introduction to the study, even the internet network constraints on the island make it difficult for students to access online services. This of course reduces the interest of students to access online learning assistance. This condition has also been understood by UT, so for students who are having difficulties with online tutorials during the covid-19 pandemic, they are given coursework services that are sent to them to work on so that they are able to practice their abilities in learning.

Online Teaching Material Services Affect the Quality of Online Learning

The results showed that online teaching materials services had no effect on the quality of online learning, so hypothesis (H3) was rejected. This is because in general students are familiar with online teaching material services in each semester before the implementation of online tutorials, so these services are not part of the indicators that can affect the quality of online learning. This result is not in line with Utami's research (2020) which shows that textbooks and references have an effect on student learning achievement. But what is interesting in this study, the value of the online teaching material service variable which is negative, indicates that students actually do not fully expect online teaching material services. As stated in the introduction to the study, even the internet network constraints on the island make it difficult for students to access online services.

Final Exam Services Affect The Quality Of Online Learning

The results showed that the final examination service had an effect on student achievement, so the hypothesis (H4) was accepted. These results are in accordance with the results of the description which show that in general students are satisfied with the service of access to manuscripts, facilities, exam schedules are well available and the final exam scores obtained are objectively in accordance with student learning outcomes. do the test. The results of this study are in line with the research of Juges et al. (2003) which shows that exams can affect student achievement or the quality of online learning.

VI. CONCLUSION

UT's online services which consist of online registration, online tutorials and online teaching materials do not affect the quality of online learning. While online exam services affect the quality of online learning. This is in line with the concept of a distance learning system, where the final exam is a determining factor in maintaining the quality standard of educational services. While the implementation of registration, learning assistance such as tutorials and teaching materials, are learning services that must be carried out as flexibly as possible so that students have alternatives in choosing the services provided.

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